

Synthesis of New Derivatives of β -Lactam-containing Antibiotics formed with certain Sulphonyl Chlorides

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6-Aminopenicillanic acid and 7-aminodeacetoxycephalosporanic acid react with a number of sulphonyl chloride derivatives, including 4-acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride, phenylacetic acid-4-sulphonyl chloride and uracil-5-sulphonyl chloride to form new family of compounds. Among the products, which showed promising antibacterial activity, the 6-(5-uracil sulphonyl)-aminopenicillanic acid (**1c**) and its cephalosporanic acid analogue (**2c**) are most active.

Penicillins (**1a**) and cephalosporins (**2a**) represent two examples of powerful antibiotics, both containing reactive β -lactam unit which is substituted with an acylamino function *cis* to the sulphur in the fused heterocycle¹. Since the mechanism of action of penicillins and cephalosporins is thought to involve irreversible acylation of a key enzyme on the outer surface of the cell membrane by the strained β -lactam system², modifications directly at the β -lactam should have profound effects upon antimicrobial activity. Numerous semisynthetic β -lactam containing antibiotics have been made since the successful cleavage of penicillin and cephalosporin C to 6-aminopenicillanic acid³ (**1b**) (6APA) and 7-aminodeacetoxycephalosporanic acid⁴ (7ADCA) (**2b**). These semisynthetic antibiotics have been derived by the acylation of the corresponding acid⁵.

The need for new therapeutic agents to combat pathogens that have developed resistance to the established antibiotics stimulated us to synthesise new semisynthetic penicillins and cephalosporins containing the sulphamyl moiety at the amino group in the β -lactam ring of both 6APA and 7ADCA.

Results and Discussion

The antibacterial compounds were obtained with the reaction of 6-aminopenicillanic acid (**1b**) and 7-aminodeacetoxycephalosporanic acid (**2b**) with 4-acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride, phenylacetic-4-sulphonyl chloride and uracil-5-sulphonyl chloride (Scheme 1). The structure of these compounds were confirmed by microanalysis and spectral analysis (Table 1).

Antimicrobial analysis : Compounds **1c,d,e** and **2c,d,e** were evaluated against four Gram-positive bacteria *Sarcina lutea*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptococcus faecalis* (Enterococcus Group D), five Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Haemophilus influenzae*.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.**	M.p., ^o C/ (Yield%)	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)
1c^a	180–83d (34)	1 680 (C=O of CH ₃ -CO), 1 770 (C=O of β -lactam), 1 780 (C=O of COOH), 1 590, 1 525 (C=C aromatic), 3 350 (NH), 1 090 (S=O), 1 220 (C–N), 790 (4-adjacent), 2 980 (C–H), 1 400 (C–H bend.)
1d^a	183 (31)	1 650 (C=O of CH ₃ -CO), 1 780 (C=O of β -lactam), 1 740 (C=O of COOH), 1 540, 1 520 (C=C aromatic), 3 340 (NH), 1 040 (S=O), 1 210 (C–N), 790 (4-adjacent), 2 840 (CH ₂), 2 995 (C–H), 1 450 (C–H bend.)
1e^a	212–15 (41)	1 780 (C=O of β -lactam), 1 740 (C=O of COOH), 1 680 (C=O of cyclic amide), 1 610 (C=C of aromatic), 3 400 (NH), 1 090 (S=O), 1 220 (C–N), 2 990 (C–H), 1 360 (C–H bend.), 1 520 (NH bend.), 1 310 (OH bend.)
2c^b	173–75 (38)	1 680 (C=O of CH ₃ CO), 1 770 (C=O of β -lactam), 1 800 (C=O of COOH), 1 580, 1 530 (C=C aromatic), 3 380 (NH), 1 080 (S=O), 1 260 (C–N), 780 (4-adjacent), 2 940 (C–H), 1 410 (C–H bend.)
2d^b	180 (16)	1 790 (C=O of β -lactam), 1 720 (C=O of COOH), 1 620, 1 520 (C=C aromatic), 3 450 (NH), 1 070 (S=O), 1 230 (C–N), 780 (4-adjacent), 2 820 (CH ₂), 2 980 (C–H), 1 410 (C–H bend.)
2e^a	195 (49)	1 760 (C=O of β -lactam), 1 740 (C=O of COOH), 1 680 (C=O of cyclic amide), 3 405 (NH), 1 065 (S=O), 1 220 (C–N), 2 970 (C–H), 1 410 (C–H bend.), 1 590 (NH bend.) and 1 350 (OH bend.)

¹H nmr : **1c** 1.17 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.62 (3H, s, CH₃ gem methyl), 4.40 (1H, s, N-CH-COO), 5.06, 5.52 (each 1H, q, N-CH-CH), 7.55 (4H, s, ArH), 10.10 (1H, bs, COOH); **1e** 1.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.62 (3H, s, CH₃ gem dimethyl), 4.42 (1H, s, N-CH-COO), 5.10, 5.54 (each 1H, q, N-CH-CH), 7.61 (1H, t, H-6 of uracil), 8.46 (2H, s, 2-NH of uracil), 11.00 (1H, bs, COOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ **1c** 260, 230; **1e** 258, 230; **2c** 256, 230; **2e** 266, 230 nm.

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

**Method of preparation : ^amethod A; ^bmethod B.

Method - A

Method - B

1c, d, synthesized via method A & B

Scheme 1

against *Proteus sp.*, *Klebsiella aerogenes* and *Serratia marcescens* and two fungi *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*.

The standard agar plate diffusion technique⁶ was used to determine the minimum inhibitory concentrations of the tested compounds. The antibacterial activity was evaluated in agarised media. The antifungal activity was assayed in agarised media (Dox medium). Dimethylsulphoxide was used as the solvent for the compounds. Ampicillin and cephalaxine were used as standard antibiotics for comparison against the bacterial and fungal species. The results are presented in Table 2.

The compounds showed no significant inhibitory effect as antifungal agents. Compound **1c** was found superior to

ampicillin against *S. aureus*, *S. marcescens*, *Proteus sp.* and *S. lutea*; similar antibiotic activity against *E. coli*, *H. influenzae* and *K. aerogenes*; but decreased antibiotic activity against *B. subtilis* and *S. faecalis*. Compound **1d** had similar activity as ampicillin. Compound **1e** was found superior to ampicillin against *S. lutea*, *S. aureus* and *S. marcescens*; similar activity against *H. influenzae*, *K. aerogenes*; but decreased activity against *B. subtilis*, *S. faecalis* and *E. coli*. Compound **2c** had higher activity than cephalaxine against *S. faecalis*, *H. influenzae*, *K. aerogenes* and *Proteus sp.*, but decreased activity against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *S. marcescens*. Compound **2d** exhibited higher activity than cephalaxine against *S. lutea*, *S. faecalis*, *H. influenzae*, *K. aerogenes* and *Proteus sp.* Compound **2e** exhibited activity against both types of bacteria. Compared to cephalaxine, **2e** was found more active against *S. lutea*, *S. faecalis*, *H. influenzae*, *Proteus sp.* and *S. marcescens*. In general, 6-(5-uracilsulphonyl)-aminopenicillanic acid (**1e**) and its cephalosporanic acid analogue (**2e**) showed most promising antibacterial activity, the latter being the most active.

Experimental

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Beckman DU70 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a QMN FX 90 GST spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Method A : Synthesis of 1c-e and 2e : A mixture of 6APA or 7ADCA (0.05 mol) in methylene chloride (100 ml) and methanol (25 ml) was cooled to -5°, then TEA (20 ml) was gradually added to it while stirring for 45 min and filtered. An equimolar amount from the requisite sulphonyl chloride derivative was then added to the cooled filtrate (-20°) and the reaction mixture was left at -10° for 2 h while its pH was kept at 4.8. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice-cold water (0-5°) and the resulting product separated.

Method B: Synthesis of 2c,d : A mixture of 7ADCA (3.5 g, 0.016 mol), acetamide (2.28 g, 0.039 mol), hexamethyldisilathine (HMDS) (3.65 ml) and tributylbenzoylammonium chloride (0.02 g, 6 × 10⁻⁵ mol) in

 TABLE 2-ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY DATA (MIC, $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) OF COMPOUNDS

Species	Ampicillin	1c	1d	1e	Cephalaxine	2c	2d	2e
<i>B. subtilis</i>	30	175	30	175	30	175	> 200	30
<i>S. lutea</i>	200	175	175	30	200	200	30	30
<i>S. aureus</i> 317	16	10	20	10	25	-	40	25
<i>S. faecalis</i>	2	5	10	10	60	40	40	30
<i>E. coli</i>	30	30	30	> 200	30	> 200	30	100
<i>H. influenzae</i>	2	2	2	2	120	110	100	110
<i>K. aerogenes</i>	500	500	> 500	500	260	230	180	-
<i>Proteus sp.</i>	500	370	500	500	250	160	130	200
<i>S. marcescens</i>	> 200	80	200	30	130	200	200	30

methylene chloride (40 ml) was refluxed (40°) for 2 h. The mixture was then cooled (-20 to -10°) and an equivalent amount of the sulphonyl chloride derivative was added. The reaction mixture was left at 0° for 2 h and at 25° for 1 h. Then the mixture was poured in ice-water and the separated solid was dried under reduced pressure at 40° to give the desired product.

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